

The Approach X : Ontology Population from French Classified Ads

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Abstract. Understanding texts written in natural language is a challenging task. Semantic Web technologies, in particular ontologies, can be used to represent knowledge from a specific domain and reason like a human. Ontology population from texts aims to transform textual contents into ontological assertions. This paper deals with an approach of automatic ontology population from French textual descriptions. This approach has been designed to be domain-independent, as long as a domain ontology is provided. It relies on text-based and knowledge-based analyses, which are fully explained. Experiments performed on French classified advertisements are discussed and provide encouraging results.

Keywords: Ontology population · Knowledge engineering · OWL

1 Introduction

Ontologies [17] are designed to share domain knowledge between humans and machines. They include a hierarchy of classes and relationships between them. Ontology population is the process of adding instances to an ontology. A populated ontology may also be referred to as a knowledge base or knowledge graph.

The approach proposed in this paper is the first part of the DECA project (Detection of Errors and Correction of Annotations). This project deals with annotated descriptions, i.e., descriptions that are in the form of texts to which annotations are appended. For example, this is the case of classified advertisements, annotated with the criteria they meet. Annotations are theoretically meant to describe characteristics of the object or event described in the description. However, this is not always the case. In fact, erroneous annotations may frequently be observed, either due to typing errors or “misuse”: descriptions are deliberately wrongly annotated to increase their visibility. For example, one can find a real estate advertisement annotated with the city X , while the description states “30 minutes from X ”; or where the area annotation (in m^2) is 150, whereas the description states “147 m^2 ”. These wrongly annotated descriptions waste a considerable amount of time for users, who must sort through the multiple responses that comply, in theory, with their search criteria. The DECA project deals with this problem. Its goal is to detect and correct erroneous annotations by leveraging the inconsistencies that can be detected based on the content expressed in the textual description. This requires understanding the text, which is the

focus of our contribution. Indeed, our goal is to populate a domain ontology from textual descriptions of objects. Our first use case concerns house sale ads, but the proposed approach must be as generic as possible, i.e., it must be able to populate a domain ontology from descriptions in various domains, whether they are classified ads (car sales, fashion, etc.), or descriptions of a certain type of object (restaurants, hotels, etc.). A domain ontology is considered as input; its design is not the object of our work.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the related work and positions our contribution. Section 3 describes our approach. Section 4 evaluates the approach while Section 5 concludes and suggests future work.

2 Related work and positioning

Ontology population has been studied in various papers [11]. In this section, we focus only on approaches aiming to extract information from unstructured textual documents and a domain ontology, allowing additions of instances in it, in particular additions of property assertions. Existing systems are based on various rule-based methods using lexico-syntactic patterns (see next paragraph); on methods based on machine learning [9,18]; or on hybrid methods [3]. Some recent approaches use deep learning [2,6]. In general, the use of machine learning techniques requires a large quantity of sentences and their ontological correspondence upstream, which is not the case for our data. We therefore concentrate on approaches exploiting lexico-syntactic patterns.

The ArtEquAKT approach [1] deals with ontology population from the Web in the domain of artists. This approach populates the ontology with property assertions. It uses the verb found in a sentence between two instances of concepts from the ontology. On the same principle, Makki [12] also focuses on verbs in order to populate the ontology with property assertions, but it is semi-automatic and domain-independent. A list of verbs is extracted from the input corpus for each property from the ontology using Wordnet. A set of seven manually written rules is used to recognise subjects and objects of a potential property assertion. Results are then validated by an expert. In [5], a framework is proposed. The goal is to instantiate a concept as well as the relationships that concern it. First, named entities are identified in the text (exploiting also co-references). Second, triggers are considered, i.e., property names as well as their synonyms; and rules are built based on noun phrases preceded or followed by a trigger. The application of these rules leads to the population of the ontology. [15] presents an approach to populate an ontology of criminal events and their causes from Spanish newspaper tweets. It is based on linguistic patterns. [10] aims at extracting property assertions in regulatory documents between incidents and actions (the “hasMeasure” property and its sub-properties) based on rules. They use both co-occurrences of incidents and measures within the same sentence, paragraph or chapter, but this does not distinguish sub-properties, for which lexical patterns are used. [14] presents a rule-based approach to extract relations from musical tidbits to populate a domain ontology. For this, rules based on grammatical la-

being are used. The study of these approaches shows several emerging scientific obstacles. In general, rule-based methods have good precision at the expense of recall [4]. Either the rules are domain-specific (lexical patterns and some very precise syntactic patterns), or the rules are generic and cannot be as precise as rules defined for a single domain. Moreover, many of these works require human intervention to validate the propositions. Furthermore, verbs are generally very important in the population of properties, as they strongly characterize relations (e.g., “is married to”). Finally, most approaches deal with named entities as subjects and objects of properties and focus on populating object properties neglecting data properties.

In our case, we aim to apply a similar approach across multiple domains, while remaining in the context of textual descriptions of objects. Since the proposed approach will be the first step towards automated annotation correction, it must be automatic, without any human validation, and sufficiently generic. In general, verbs are not very characteristic of a relation in object descriptions (e.g., “have” or “possess”). Sometimes, there is no verb at all (e.g., “2 bedrooms, 1 bathroom.”), which complicates the population. We wish to populate both object and data properties. Subjects and objects are not necessarily named entities. Finally, our context may present ternary properties. Automatic population of n-ary properties has, to our knowledge, never been studied. For all these reasons, the cited works are not adapted to our original problem, which necessitates a novel approach.

3 The X-approach

We present X-approach, an approach to populate a domain ontology from textual descriptions of elements of this domain. It takes as input a corpus of descriptions and a domain ontology and populates the ontology by representing the descriptions of the corpus.

3.1 Initial data

The input ontology defines the domain. It can be defined as a tuple $(\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ where \mathcal{C} is a set of classes, \mathcal{P} a set of (object and data) properties characterizing the classes, \mathcal{I} a set of individuals and assertions (potentially empty), \mathcal{A} a set of axioms representable in OWL2 (Web Ontology Language) and \mathcal{R} a set of SWRL (Semantic Web Rule Language) [8] rules (potentially empty). The domain is represented by a class named hereafter *main class*. Data properties taken into account can use boolean values, numerical values or strings. The ontology can contain initial individuals, which are generic. Each entity of the ontology (class, property, individual) has an identifier (URI) and possibly more advanced terminology, via `rdfs:label`, `rdfs:isDefinedBy`, as well as a “unit” annotation property, especially created to associate an entity with a unit or a unit expression (exemplified in the following). The ontology may exist beforehand or be created: its design is not part of our contribution. The input corpus is composed of French

documents, each of which describes an instance of the *main class*. Figures 2-3 show one example of a description.

Fig. 1. Partial vision of the entities of our French house sales ontology

Cormelles-le-Royal : Magnifique maison à 15 min du centre-ville de Caen et à 3 min à pied des commerces et des écoles, 110 m² sur un terrain de 400 m². Le rez-de-chaussée est composé d'une cuisine équipée, d'un salon avec cheminée, exposé sud-ouest, ainsi que d'une chambre de 15 m². Premier étage : 2 chambres et 1 sdb. Proche des transports en commun. Terrain arboré et clos. Honoraires : 4%.

Fig. 2. A French house sale ad

Cormelles-le-Royal : Magnificent house located 15 min from the city center of Caen and 3 min walk from shops and schools, 110 m² on a land of 400 m². The ground floor consists of a kitchen equipped with essential appliances, a living room with fireplace, facing southwest, as well as a bedroom of 15 m². First floor: 2 bedrooms and 1 bathroom. Close to public transport. Wooded and enclosed land. Fees : 4%.

Fig. 3. Translation of Fig. 2

Color legend for the matchings: Individuals Classes Object properties Data properties

The approach is designed to be applicable to different domains. The example unfolded in this paper considers the domain of house sales. Figure 1 represents a partial view of the classes and properties of the ontology used in this domain. It contains classes such as the main class *Property* (denoting real estate), *Room*, *Kitchen*, etc. Among the ontology properties, we can cite the object property *isLocatedIn* linking a real estate property to a municipality, or the data property *areaInM2* connecting a real estate *property part* (land, house, etc.) or a *room* to a numerical value. The initial individuals are generic, e.g., instances of the classes *Municipality* or *HeatingSystem*. The ontology also contains axioms, for example, the fact that a real estate *Property* can only be located in at most one *Municipality*. Units are used, e.g., *areaInM2* with the unit “m²”, or *feePercentage* with a unit expression “fees: xxx %”. This representation of units is basic and could be improved in a future version.

3.2 Proposed framework

The proposed approach must be applicable to different types of objects. For a given domain, it is necessary to have as input a domain ontology as well as a corpus of documents, where each document is a text that describes an instance of the *main class*. Thus, the proposed algorithm must not depend on domain-based rules or linguistic models. Therefore, we chose to use domain terminology (from the ontology), syntactic indicators (such as sentences or the order of expressions in the text) and knowledge indicators (such as property domains and ranges).

Fig. 4. Outline of the X-approach

Figure 4 shows the outline of the approach. The ontology (O), as well as a document from the corpus, are used (top of the Figure) by a terminology matcher. This leads to matchings between text mentions and entities of O . Then, a population algorithm is applied, which is a processing chain (middle of the Figure): an initialisation of an object called “Matching Handler” (MH); an instantiation of the *main class*; a textual analysis, composed of various modules (bottom of the Figure); as well as an analysis based on the knowledge of the ontology. This process is applied on each document of the corpus. At the end, the output populated ontology represents all the descriptions of the corpus. The remaining of this section details each module using the document example from Figures 2-3.

3.3 The terminology matcher

The terminology matcher is the first step of the approach. It takes as input the initial ontology and a document, and produces matchings between the textual mentions and entities of the ontology. The text is split into sentences and lemmatized. The ontology’s keywords (URI fragments, labels, units) are also lemmatized. Matchings are established between the text and the ontology’s keywords. Snake_case and camelCase conventions are taken into account. These also concern unit expressions, e.g., the mention *fees: 4%* matches the unit expression *fees: xxx %*. All matchings contained in another matching are removed. For example, if there is a matching on the mention “city center” and on its sub-mention “city”, only the one on “city center” is considered.

In Figures 2-3, matchings concern individuals (e.g., “ground floor” \leftrightarrow *ground-Floor*), classes (“house” \leftrightarrow *House*), object properties (“Close to” \leftrightarrow *isCloseTo*)

or data properties (“m²” \leftrightarrow *areaInM2*). Our use case is in French but examples are translated into English in the following.

3.4 The population algorithm

Matchings are inputs of the population algorithm. It has four main tasks (see Figure 4), the first two of which are pre-processing. The third, called text-based analysis, is a population task using matchings and textual indicators. The last task, called knowledge-based analysis, adds property assertions based on the ontology’s knowledge. These tasks are described in the remaining of this section.

The two pre-processing tasks The first task consists in initialising the matching handler $MH = \{mh_1, mh_2, \dots, mh_n\}$, a set used thorough the algorithm. Each mh corresponds to a matching and contains three attributes (individuals, assertions, previous linked individuals) initially empty.

The next task consists in instantiating the main class, to represent the document being processed. Hence, a new individual, hereafter called the *main instance*, instance of the main class, is added to O . In our document example, the individual *property1* is created with the assertion $\langle property1, isA, Property \rangle$ (*Property* being the main class, representing a real estate property).

Text-based analysis This task is detailed at the bottom of Figure 4. It analyses the matchings, adds individuals and assertions thanks to textual indicators.

Class matching processing Each matching with a class (except the main class) is analyzed, to create a new individual, instance of this class. For the studied document example, the update of MH (added individuals and assertions) can be observed on the rows whose type is “class” in Table 1. These individuals and assertions are added to O . The preceding word(s) of a matching are checked against a list of negation keywords (e.g., “no”), and the matching is disregarded if a negation indicator is detected (e.g., “no garage”). If the preceding word corresponds to a number, multiple individuals are generated accordingly (e.g., “2 bedrooms” creates two instances of the class *Bedroom*).

Individual matching processing Then, MH is updated for the matchings with individuals of O , by adding them. This can be observed on the rows corresponding to the type “individual” in Table 1.

Property matching processing To instantiate a property, we need to determine the subject and object of the assertion. Subject candidate matchings are browsed, starting from the one preceding the property matching, going back to the beginning of the sentence. As soon as a candidate mh has individual(s) belonging to the property domain, these individual(s) are subject candidate(s). As for the objects, it depends on the type of the property. For object properties, we consider the matching immediately following the property mention. If such a matching exists, the individuals in its mh that are in the property range are considered as

possible objects. For data properties, the options vary based on the range and the matching source (e.g., unit or unit expression).

For each possible subject and object, a property assertion is added, provided that it does not create an inconsistency in O . The mh is updated: the new assertion(s) and their subject individual(s) are added respectively to the attributes *assertions* and *individuals*. The mh representing the object is also updated: the subject of the assertion is added in its attribute *previous linked individuals* (exploited in the following). If no assertion can be added, then the process is repeated with a new instance of the property domain as subject. Once all property matchings have been processed, all individuals in O that are inferred as equivalent are merged, and MH is updated based on this merger.

Table 1. MH after dealing with class, individual and property matchings

Matching	Type	Individuals	Assertions	Prev. ind.
Cormelles-le-R.	individual	Cormelles-le-R		
house	class	house1	<house1, isA, House>	
located	object property			
min	data property	distance1	<distance1, isA, Distance> <distance1, minCar, 15>	
city center	individual	city_center		
Caen	individual	Caen		
min walk	data property	distance1 distance2	<distance1, minWalk, 3> <distance2, isA, Distance> <distance2, minWalk, 3>	
shops	individual	shops		
schools	individual	schools		
m ²	data property	house1	<house1, areaInM2, 110>	
land	class	land1	<land1, isA, Land>	
m ²	data property	land1	<land1, areaInM2, 400>	
ground floor	individual	groundFloor		
kitchen	class	kitchen1	<kitchen1, isA, Kitchen>	
equipped	data property	kitchen1	<kitchen1, equipped, true>	
living room	class	livingRoom1	<livingRoom1, isA, LivingRoom>	
fireplace	class	fireplace1	<fireplace1, isA, Fireplace>	
facing	data property	livingRoom1	<livingRoom1, exposure, southwest>	
bedroom	class	bedroom1	<bedroom1, isA, Bedroom>	
m ²	data property	bedroom1	<bedroom1, areaInM2, 15>	
First floor	individual	firstFloor		
bedrooms	class	bedroom2 bedroom3	<bedroom2, isA, Bedroom> <bedroom3, isA, Bedroom>	
bathroom	class	bathroom1	<bathroom1, isA, Bathroom>	
Close to	object property	property1	<property1, isCloseTo, pubTransport>	
public transport	individual	pubTransport		property1
Land	class	land2	<land2, isA, Land>	
Fees : 4%	data property	property1	<property1, feePercentage, 4>	

Table 1 shows the property matching handler on the example (cf. rows whose type is a property). First, the mention “located” refers to the object property *isLocatedIn* whose range is a municipality. It is not followed by a matching on a municipality: the property cannot be instantiated. The matching on “min” refers to the property *minCar* associating a distance to a numerical value in minutes. Its source is a unit (“min” is a unit associated with this property), so

we consider the previous word for the value: 15. There is no instance of the class *Distance*, so the set of possible subjects is initially empty, and we take a new instance of *Distance* (*distance1*). Note that new individuals are named according to the class of which they are instances (for example, *distance1* and *distance2* for the class *Distance*); if the domain to instantiate is a class expression, then the new individuals are named *indiv1*, *indiv2*, etc. For the matching on “min walk”, the process is the same, except that the set of possible subjects considers *distance1* since it is an individual resulting from a matching preceding the one being processed, from the same sentence, and in the property domain. Therefore, we try to add an assertion $\langle \textit{distance1}, \textit{minWalk}, 3 \rangle$ but this one is inconsistent, because *distance1* already represents 15 min by car. Thus, a new subject individual *distance2* is created. All the assertions added are in the table. Note that, as the matching on “Close to” leads to the assertion $\langle \textit{property1}, \textit{isCloseTo}, \textit{publicTransport} \rangle$, *property1* is a previous linked individual in the *mh* of “public transport”.

Initialisation of the linkabilities In a descriptive context, verbs are not very meaningful (see Section 2). It is very likely to miss property assertions, due to an absence of property matching. The remaining of the population algorithm aims to add property assertions. To this end, we introduce an element called the linkabilities (*Lnk*). Its initialisation consists in creating all the linkabilities $Lnk(i)$ for each individual *i* from *MH*. An element of $Lnk(i)$ is a pair (*property*, *range class expression*), such that *i* is linkable (via the property) to an individual belonging to the range class expression. In other words, for an individual *i*, we look for each property *prop* for which *i* can be a subject. Then, we look for the range expression to which an object *obj* of a possible assertion $\langle i, \textit{prop}, \textit{obj} \rangle$ must necessarily belong. The set $Lnk(i)$ is automatically built for each *i*.

In the example, *property1* belongs to the domain of *contains*, establishing a linkability. Now, *property1* is an instance of *Property*, which is a subclass of the expression *contains only PartOfProperty*. Thus, the range expression associated with *property1* and *contains* is the intersection of the range of *contains* (i.e., *PartOfProperty* or *Rooms*) and the class *PartOfProperty* (based on the definition with *only*). Therefore, the tuple (*contains*, *PartOfProperty*) is a linkability for *property1*. This means that *property1* can only serve as the subject of an assertion of *contains* with instances of *PartOfProperty*.

The linkabilities $Lnk(i)$ are used in the following steps to find the most suitable property to link a subject *i* with an object *j*. The set $Lnk(i)$ will be browsed until a linkability is found such that *j* belongs to its range expression. $Lnk(i)$ is a sorted set. When several properties are candidates, finding the best one is not trivial. We give priority to specificity. The first elements are the linkabilities whose range is the most specific, then those whose property domain is the most specific. Otherwise, the sorting is arbitrarily, according to the property URI.

Processing of the consecutive matchings This step checks if it is possible to link the individual(s) resulting from a matching with the one(s) from the following matching in the text, coming from the same sentence. Property assertions are

added whenever it is possible. N-ary properties are taken into account. A succession of matchings involving respectively individuals a , b and c may lead to property assertions of the type $\langle a, \dots, b \rangle$ and $\langle a, \dots, c \rangle$. Here, the goal is to link a and b , which are from consecutive matchings, but also a and c , which are not.

The idea is to check if an individual (*subject*) from the current matching can be connected to an individual (*object*) from the next matching. If there are no associated individuals in the next *mh*, we move to the next one until we find an individual. If *subject* and *object* are not already connected, there might be a missing assertion. To determine the best property between these individuals, we consider the sorted set $Lnk(subject)$ and select the first property where *object* is in the range expression of the linkability and does not introduce any inconsistencies to O . The assertion is added in the subject’s *mh*, and *subject* is also added as a previous linked individual of the object’s *mh*. If there is no possible assertion between consecutive matchings, we attempt to make an assertion with the previous linked individuals as the subject to facilitate the population of n-ary properties. After examining the entire text, equivalent individuals in O are merged, and MH is updated accordingly.

Table 2. MH of the example after the processing of the consecutive matchings

Matching	Individuals	Assertions	Prev. linked ind.
Cormelles-le-R.	Cormelles-le-R.		
house	house1	$\langle house1, isA, House \rangle$	
located			
min	distance1	$\langle distance1, isA, Distance \rangle$ $\langle distance1, minCar, 15 \rangle$ $\langle distance1, distFromPI, city center \rangle$ (1)	
city center	city center	$\langle distance1, distFromCity, Caen \rangle$ (2)	distance1 (1)
Caen	Caen		distance1 (2)
min walk	distance2	$\langle distance2, isA, Distance \rangle$ $\langle distance2, minWalk, 3 \rangle$ $\langle distance2, distFromPI, shops \rangle$ (3)	
shops	shops	$\langle distance2, distFromPI, schools \rangle$ (4)	distance2 (3)
schools	schools		distance2 (4)
...
living room	livingRoom1	$\langle livingRoom1, isA, LivingRoom \rangle$ $\langle livingRoom1, hasElement, fireplace1 \rangle$ (5)	
fireplace	fireplace1	$\langle fireplace1, isA, Fireplace \rangle$	livingRoom1 (5)
...

Table 2 shows the MH of the example after this step. First, we try to connect *Cormelles-le-R.* to *house1* (impossible), then *house1* to *distance1* (impossible), etc. We can connect *distance1* to *city center* via the property *distanceFrom-PointOfInterest* (1). The assertion is added in the subject *mh* (on the mention “min”). The next *mh* (on “city center”) is updated with the previous linked individual *distance1*. Then, to link the *mh* on “city center” with the one on “Caen”, we cannot connect the associated individuals. Nevertheless, we can link the previous linked individual, *distance1*, to *Caen* (2). And so on, we get (3)-(4)-(5).

Processing of individuals without predecessors The last step of the text-based analysis deals with individuals without predecessors. Indeed, each document describes an instance of the main class, which should be the starting point of property assertions. It seems quite intuitive to think that every individual considered, except the main instance, must be the object of at least one assertion. Thus, the goal is to find subjects and properties for individuals (except for the main instance) without predecessors, i.e., not being the object of a property assertion. To minimise the risk of linking individuals that have nothing to do with each other, we focus only on the individuals resulting from the matchings of a same sentence. This means that, for each individual without predecessors (*object*) of a sentence, we try to connect another individual from the same sentence (*subject*) to it, in order to obtain the assertion $\langle \textit{subject}, \textit{prop}, \textit{object} \rangle$, where the property *prop* is the “best” regarding the linkabilities. Finally, any individuals in *O* that are inferred as equivalent are merged, and *MH* is updated based on this merger.

Fig. 5. Individuals and property assertions from the studied example, before the processing of the individuals without predecessors

Figure 5 shows the individuals (nodes) and property assertions (edges) before this step for the studied example. Individuals without predecessors (except the main instance *property1*) are shaded. Table 3 details what is done at this stage. Each row corresponds to a sentence. Individuals without predecessors are in italics. For each of them, we search if it is possible to add an assertion having for subject an individual of the same sentence. The only two possibilities for the first sentence are given in the last column but they are not added because they are inconsistent. This principle is repeated for each sentence. The assertions mentioned in Table 3 are obtained and added in *O* and *MH*.

Knowledge-based analysis The last task is based on the knowledge from *O*. It exploits *O*, *MH* and *Lnk*. Ideally, from the main instance, all the individuals concerned by a document should be reachable. The goal is to add property assertions to establish a connected graph, starting from the main instance. Figure 6 (top) shows the individuals (nodes) and object property assertions (edges) of the studied example. Only *publicTransport* is reachable from *property1*.

Table 3. The processing of the individuals without predecessors in the studied example

#	Individuals	Assertions
1	<i>Cormelles-le-Royal</i> , <i>house1</i> , <i>distance1</i> , city center, Caen, <i>distance2</i> , shops, schools, <i>land1</i>	<distance1, distFromCity, <i>Cormelles-le-R.</i> > <distance2, distFromCity, <i>Cormelles-le-R.</i> > not added because inconsistent
2	<i>groundFloor</i> , <i>kitchen1</i> , <i>livingRoom1</i> , fireplace1, <i>bedroom1</i>	<kitchen1, isOnFloor, <i>groundFloor</i> > <livingRoom1, isOnFloor, <i>groundFloor</i> > <bedroom1, isOnFloor, <i>groundFloor</i> >
3	<i>firstFloor</i> , <i>bedroom2</i> , <i>bedroom3</i> , <i>bathroom1</i>	<bedroom2, isOnFloor, <i>firstFloor</i> > <bedroom3, isOnFloor, <i>firstFloor</i> > <bathroom1, isOnFloor, <i>firstFloor</i> >
4	property1, publicTransport	
5	<i>land2</i>	
6	property1	

Individuals are put into batches, each individual being in exactly one batch. Each batch is created from an individual i and contains the individuals reachable from i (either directly or through a sequence of assertions). The *main batch* consists of the main instance and the individuals accessible from it. Then, the remaining individuals are considered: the one with the least predecessors is taken (alphabetical order of URI in case of equality), its batch is created, and the process continues until every individual is in one batch. In the studied example, the first division into batches is shown with frames at the top of Figure 6. The *main batch* is composed of *property1* and *publicTransport*. The individual with the fewest predecessors (first in alphabetical order) is *bathroom1*. The next batch consists of *bathroom1* and *firstFloor*. And so on, batches are built.

The goal is to access all the individuals from the main instance. To this end, once the batches are built, we try to link the main instance to an individual of each batch (except the main batch). Within a batch, the individuals are sorted in ascending order based on the number of predecessors (and then in alphabetical order). For each batch, we attempt to create a property assertion between the main instance (as the subject) and each individual in the given order (as the object), stopping as soon as a valid property assertion is possible. In the studied example, *distance2* is placed first in the batch $\{distance2, shops, schools\}$ because it has no predecessors. Using the linkabilities, we determine whether the main instance *property1* can be linked to *distance2*. This is the case via the property *isLocatedAtDistance*. This process is repeated for each batch, resulting in six assertions as shown in the middle of Figure 6.

Next, individuals that are inferred to be equivalent are merged, and *MH* is updated based on this merger. In our example ontology, a real estate property can contain only one land. A reasoner identifies *land1* and *land2* as equivalent. They are merged into *land1* (see bottom of Figure 6).

The same process (creating batches, adding assertions, merging) is repeated, but considering all individuals that are at a distance of 1 from the main instance as subjects, i.e., individuals for which there is an assertion between the main class and them. In other words, the distance of an individual i can be defined as

Fig. 6. Knowledge-based analysis: First division into batches (top), first additions of assertions (middle), fusion and second division into batches (bottom)

the minimal number of edges between the main instance and i . This distance is progressively incremented. We stop either when the main batch contains all individuals or when we have already attempted to link every individual in the main batch. In the example, the batch splitting algorithm is applied again, resulting in the batches shown at the bottom of Figure 6. We now search for assertions where the subject is at a distance of 1 from the main class (*Cormelles*, *distance1*, *distance2*, *house1*, *land1* and *publicTransport*). The algorithm enables us to derive six assertions: $\langle \text{house1}, \text{contains}, \text{bathroom1} / \text{bedroom1} / \text{bedroom2} / \text{bedroom3} / \text{kitchen1} / \text{livingRoom1} \rangle$. Afterwards, only one batch remains: all elements are accessible from the main instance. The process is stopped.

The example unfolded in this paper is an illustration where X-approach works well. However, the algorithm can generate wrong assertions or miss correct ones. The subsequent section evaluates the algorithm’s performance.

4 Experiments and evaluation

This section reports an evaluation of the proposed approach on one use case: house sale classified ads. X-approach is implemented in Java and uses OWL API [7] to handle the ontology; Stanford NLP [13] to split the texts into sentences; two French lemmatizers: A. Aker’s one¹ and TreeTagger [16]; and Openllet reasoner². The experimental protocol and the results obtained are discussed.

¹ <http://staffwww.dcs.shef.ac.uk/people/A.Aker/activityNLPProjects.html>

² <https://github.com/Galigator/openllet>

4.1 Experimental protocol

We automatically extracted a corpus from a website³. It contains 78 French ads, annotated as sales of a house in Caen. Structured information has been extracted, but our focus is solely on the textual descriptions of each ad. The ontology, manually built, describes the domain of house sales and adheres to the constraints mentioned in Section 3.1. Initially, it contains a few generic individuals, such as *double glazing*, *public transport*, etc., as well as named entities corresponding to city or village names. On a larger scale, we would require an extensive list of cities, but for this experiment, we chose to represent only those mentioned in the corpus. We constructed a Gold Standard ontology (GS). This GS is the initial ontology manually populated with assertions representing the corpus descriptions. We test X-approach on the initial ontology and each description from the corpus, and then compare the final ontology with the GS, computing precision, recall, and F-measure.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad F\text{-measure} = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Property assertions are defined as true positives (TP), false positives (FP) or false negatives (FN). A TP is an assertion present in both the GS and the output O . A FP is an assertion present in the output O but absent in the GS. A FN is an assertion present in the GS but absent in the output O . To be as fair as possible in our results, we set three rules. First of all, (1) class assertions are not taken into account because they are often redundant with property assertions, e.g., via domain or range definitions. Moreover, the real issue of our problem lies in the property assertions, as the class assertions are often derived from class matchings. (2) Inferred assertions are taken into account. For example, if the GS contains $\langle a, prop, b \rangle$ and the resulting ontology contains $\langle b, inverse(prop), a \rangle$, then we want to realize that these two assertions amount to the same thing. (3) We ignore properties that lead us to count several times a same element. For example, if there is a property and its inverse, we end up with two assertions designating the same thing. The assertions of one of these two are ignored.

Experimental files are available⁴. X-approach creates URIs that are not necessarily the same as the ones from the GS. To evaluate these cases, manual equivalences are defined between the individuals of the GS and those of the output ontology. Furthermore, the approach can generate equivalent individuals, without detecting their equivalence. In this case, we assume that an equivalence axiom (owl:sameAs) is missing and count it as a missing assertion (a FN).

4.2 Results and discussion

Our problem differs from related work (see Section 2), so there are no existing baselines that can be considered for a fair comparison. We evaluate X-approach

³ <https://www.lecoindelimmo.com/>

⁴ Experimental files (inputs, outputs for all tested approaches, and GS) are at <https://zenodo.org/records/10688145>.

and analyze the contribution of its main modules. The first baseline we use, called *Baseline*, consists in processing only the class, individual and property matchings (the first three steps of the text-based analysis). Then, in *Baseline+cons.*, we add the processing of the consecutive matchings (and the initialisation of linkabilities). In *Text-based analysis*, we include the processing of individuals without predecessors, and finally in *X-approach*, we add the knowledge-based analysis.

Table 4. Results on X-approach and three baselines

Approach	Prec. _{mac}	Recall _{mac}	F-measure _{mac}	Prec. _{mic}	Recall _{mic}	F-measure _{mic}
X-approach _{Aker}	0.9516	0.8740	0.9079	0.9465	0.8606	0.9015
X-approach _{TT}	0.9496	0.8681	0.9039	0.9446	0.8545	0.8973
Text-based analysis _{Aker}	0.8989	0.4648	0.5994	0.8956	0.4726	0.6188
Text-based analysis _{TT}	0.8964	0.4579	0.5929	0.8937	0.4662	0.6127
Baseline+cons. _{Aker}	0.8911	0.3138	0.4440	0.8741	0.3085	0.4561
Baseline+cons. _{TT}	0.8879	0.3081	0.4377	0.8732	0.3036	0.4505
Baseline _{Aker}	0.9234	0.1922	0.3099	0.9135	0.1926	0.3182
Baseline _{TT}	0.9230	0.1888	0.3054	0.9138	0.1892	0.3135

Table 4 shows the results. Approaches are tested with the two lemmatizers (*Aker* and *TT*). Each metric is computed both macroscopically (*mac*) and microscopically (*mic*). The macro-computation is the average of the metrics of each ad (each ad has the same weight), whereas the micro-computation considers the sum of all VP, FP, FN of each ad (each assertion has the same weight).

Aker performs better than *TreeTagger*, but the difference is relatively low. The added modules have a good contribution on the results, since the addition of each one generates a relatively high gain of F-measure. First, the baseline achieves a relatively high precision score (> 0.9) but a low recall score (< 0.2). Most of the assertions that are made are correct, but a lot of assertions are missing. Adding modules enables us to include mostly correct assertions. Indeed, as modules are added, we are able to increase the recall without losing to much precision. More precisely, the consecutive matching processing introduces some noise (resulting in a slight loss of precision) but increases the recall by half (from ~ 0.2 to ~ 0.3). Processing individuals without predecessors also increases the recall by half (from ~ 0.3 to ~ 0.45), without a noticeable decrease in precision (slightly increasing it). Lastly, the knowledge-based analysis makes a significant contribution. It results in an increase in both precision and recall, leading to a 50% increase in F-measure (from ~ 0.6 to ~ 0.9). These three modules are essential as they add numerous missing assertions while maintaining a low number of false assertions.

5 Conclusion and future work

This paper presents X-approach, a fully automatic generic approach to populate a domain ontology from textual descriptions of objects in that domain. X-approach is a processing chain that yields promising results in its initial ex-

periment. Its algorithm is based solely on the context of the problem (textual descriptions of objects) rather than relying on domain-specific linguistic rules.

In future work, we will experiment the approach on new domains: other types of ads (such as boat sales), various descriptions (hotels, restaurants, etc.). Of course, this is time-consuming: constitution of the corpus, of the ontology, of the gold standard, as well as potential equivalences between the gold standard and the X-approach output ontology, and potential missing equivalence links in the output. Another idea is to test X-approach on the same domain and corpus but with different ontologies (same terminology but different representation choices). A deep analysis of such an experiment could lead to a set of guidelines for representing the input ontology. Lastly, our final goal is to use X-approach followed by a reasoning step to address the problem of erroneous annotations mentioned in Section 1. The main idea is to deal with inconsistencies between the output triples of X-approach and the annotations. For example, if X-approach states that a house is in *city_1*, whereas the annotation states it is in *city_2* (different from *city_1*), then this inconsistency needs to be handled.

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